

IMPROVING HUMANITY AND INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION IN STUDENTS' RELATIONSHIPS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the factors of improving humanitarian and international education in the interaction of students. The main goal of the article is to discuss the extent to which humanitarian and cultural elements are interrelated and the factors of instilling trans lingual and transcultural concepts into students.*

Keywords: *globalization, foreign culture, national identity, society, nation, country, ethics, patriotism, cultural tolerance.*

It is widely known that no matter what happens in any part of the world, people will immediately find out about it in the other part of the world. In other words, globalization has brought people all over the world into closer contact than ever before. **The introductory** part of the article talks about the process of globalization and the correct formation of international culture and humanitarian concepts in students by means of learning foreign languages.

In our country, in the formation of tolerance towards this globalization among young people, great attention is paid to the harmony of moral values, education of the culture of harmony, development of effective methods of developing a new spiritual worldview based on national and universal values, and ensuring a healthy spiritual environment. As the priority direction of building the foundation of the Third Renaissance, "Education of young people as a person with patriotism, sense of citizenship, tolerance, respect for laws, national and universal values, who can resist harmful influences and currents, and have firm beliefs and views on life" is defined. This requires the development of teaching technologies aimed at elucidating the content of the development of tolerance in students in the environment of foreign language education, improving the pedagogical conditions for the development of tolerance, and increasing the effectiveness of this process.

The teaching of foreign languages plays a big role in formulating and improving international education of students in higher education institutions. Foreign languages not only improve students' linguistic skills, but also help to form their international culture and education. This is because when language and cultural knowledge is accessible to all, students are personally empowered to communicate effectively with the local and global community.

The world was created in such a way that in all its times, tolerance was considered the highest human virtue. As long as the concept of tolerance is not sufficiently formed in multi-ethnic and multicultural countries, foreign nationalities and religions intolerance, violence and various conflicts against the representatives the background will be created. Foreign language lessons are of particular importance in forming the concept of intercultural tolerance in students. Because in foreign language classes, students get a lot of information about other peoples and cultures, but also learn to look at them with compassion and respect, and also to be united.

If we pay attention to the theoretical aspects of the article, intercultural tolerance means mutual tolerance, kindness, care, generosity, forgiveness, acceptance and tolerance between individuals, groups and social communities belonging to two or more cultures. It is desirable to

form the concept of intercultural tolerance, first of all, among schoolchildren and students of higher education institutions. Educating students in the spirit of tolerance, i.e. tolerance towards the way of life, behavior, feelings, ideas and beliefs of others is becoming one of the urgent problems of today. teaching methods and extracurricular activities are promoted through real interactions. This provides an opportunity to create a healthy learning environment in foreign language classes, consisting of a democratic and cooperative environment, objective assessment, teacher-student ethics and interaction, and mutual traditions and values of the learning community. In this way, students develop tolerant attitudes towards themselves, tolerance and empathy in relations between fellow students and group mates. The process of developing tolerance among students is strengthened by introducing topics and materials that shape intercultural and interpersonal relations. Thus, in recent years, attention to intercultural tolerance is increasing due to the fact that various problems caused by the introduction of "mass culture" among students have become relatively acute. Foreign language classes are an effective environment for the formation of respect for intercultural relations and the development of understanding and respect for the values of other people's cultures.

In the practical process of the article, it is discussed how much and in what way culture has a great influence on the learning process for the language learner. In general, students tend to have a negative attitude towards the foreign culture and the language they learn. It should be emphasized that the formation of intercultural tolerance in the English language classes of educational institutions where representatives of several nationalities and religions are studying has an effective result. In the organization of cooperation between such groups, as a result of revitalizing the cognitive activity of students, implementing the action of working as a team, the feeling of friendship, brotherhood, solidarity, and mutual support among the members of these groups is formed and strengthened. They gradually get used to each other and begin to tolerate each other. Such students of different nationalities and religions learn to respect each other's traditions, values, and lifestyles. At the same time, the concept of personal tolerance decreases and students become more socialized. "Foreign language" lessons have great opportunities for the formation of intercultural tolerance in students. A foreign language is a part of the multicultural environment in the school, university, social and educational environment, where the formation of tolerance is carried out in the system of intercultural, social and educational relations, promotion, assimilation of the national culture, and the formation of human values through cultural education are the conditions for learning a foreign language.

Organization of educational processes based on the requirements of the modern labor market, adaptation of teaching to new strategies, scientific and research related to professional activities of the educational information base are being carried out in world research and educational institutions. In this regard, special attention is being paid to the formation of motivation to acquire new knowledge in students, the development of student spirituality, and the need to develop intercultural tolerance as an important moral standard in each person.

In recent years, in our republic, comprehensive measures have been taken to improve the methodical support of technology education, to help students learn foreign languages on the basis of innovative approaches, and certain results are being achieved. In the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the important tasks of "fundamentally improving the quality of general secondary education, in-depth study of foreign languages, computer science and other important and high-demand subjects such as mathematics, physics,

chemistry, biology" are defined. In the implementation of these tasks, including the formation of the concept of intercultural tolerance in students, foreign language classes are of particular importance.

Two main reasons can be given for considering intercultural tolerance as an integral part of foreign language teaching. The first is that the English language has an international position, that is, as a key to communication in various fields, and the second, globalization is due to the migration of people from a different culture to a different cultural setting. This, in turn, improves the didactic system of organizing situations for the formation of intercultural tolerance competence along with students' foreign language skills, instilling modern approaches into its integrated content, clarifying the methodological possibilities of foreign language education, and developing a model of the pedagogical process aimed at forming students' intercultural tolerance competence based on modern approaches. improvement is gaining importance.

Comprehensive study of foreign languages in our country and their implementation by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 "The higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 Decree No. PQ-4884 of November 6, 2020 "On additional measures to further improve the education system", No. PQ-5117 of May 19, 2021 "On the quality of popularization of the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan" The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 31, 2019 No. 1059 "On the approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation" and other legal documents have been adopted.

Therefore, it can be concluded that in order to achieve the desired goal, the resources related to the lesson should be enriched with topics related to tolerance. Learning a language teaches to be aware of the national culture, and teaching a foreign language teaches to be tolerant of other national cultures. Taking into account the fact that foreign language teachers have the opportunity to shape the worldview of students and their values, it is also appropriate to provide them with methodological resources that serve to improve their cultural and spiritual skills.

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